

LIABILITY OF LEGAL ENTITIES IN INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY LAW

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Abstract. *In this thesis, the application of pre-trial alternatives to the liability of legal entities in intellectual property law and to the judicial review of intellectual property disputes is very necessary in modern legal systems. In the legal system of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the problems that exist in the settlement of intellectual property disputes and what steps are needed to introduce alternative settlement of disputes.*

Keywords: *civil law, intellectual property, object, intellectual activity.*

ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬ ЮРИДИЧЕСКИХ ЛИЦ В ПРАВЕ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНОЙ СОБСТВЕННОСТИ

Аннотация. *В данной диссертации применение досудебных альтернатив ответственности юридических лиц в области интеллектуальной собственности и судебного рассмотрения споров в области интеллектуальной собственности является весьма необходимым в современных правовых системах. В правовой системе Узбекистана особое внимание уделяется проблемам, существующим при разрешении споров в области интеллектуальной собственности, и тем, какие шаги необходимы для внедрения альтернативного разрешения споров.*

Ключевые слова: *гражданское право, интеллектуальная собственность, объект, интеллектуальная деятельность.*

Intellectual property is considered a special specific object of civil law. Before talking about intellectual property, it is necessary to find out the lexical meaning of this word. "Intellect "is a Latin word meaning" mind". Hence, intellectual property arises through the mental potential of a person. Objects of intellectual property are other objects of civil law - objects, from securities to the following: firstly, objects of intellectual property are manifested not in material form, but in the form of ideas, knowledge, information.

An idea expressed in an objective form, knowledge is in the material Messenger. in material expression, for example, a drawing. it can be embodied in a layout, hardware, device, but in this the idea, knowledge is primary, its material embodiment is always secondary. Secondly, the idea is that the object of intellectual property in the form of knowledge cannot be owned as if it were the possession of a typical material object. Thirdly, such objects can be used simultaneously by persons of an infinite circle. In addition, intellectual property rights, the rule on the non-existence of property rights to its objects, the validity of intellectual property rights will be limited by the deadlines established in the laws.

Also, with the expiration of the deadlines established in the laws, the rights of the owner of intellectual property in relation to a particular object of intellectual property are revoked, and these objects become universal wealth, and everyone uses it freely and without permission under certain conditions. In addition, in cases where objects of intellectual property law are in the form of an idea, they cannot be possessed like objects, the possibility of applying a vindictive claim to the protection of property rights in relation to such objects does not exist in practice due to the fact that at the same time

an unlimited range of individuals can use them. The rules regarding exclusive rights, rather than the usual property rights, apply to the objects of intellectual property law. Another important aspect is that the validity of intellectual property rights, at the same time, will also be limited to a certain territory.

Results of intellectual activity. Intellectual activity is, by its nature, the highest manifestation of human activity - creative activity. Human creative activity is different from the usual, everyday activity of human conscious activity in terms of the features of methods-means of carrying out this activity, products of activity. The usual, daily activity is a constant, repetitive activity, in which both the activity itself and the results arising from it are known from the previous one. For this reason, normal, daily activities are considered reproductive activities, in which ready-made thoughts are re-formed, repeated, based on formal logic or other rules of law. Creative activity is an intellectual activity, as a result of which a new, creative independent product is developed in the field of science, technology, literature or art.

The owner of property rights in relation to the result of intellectual activity or a means of reflecting private signs will be entitled to the exclusive legal use of this object of intellectual property at his discretion in any form, in any way. These exclusive rights are a property right according to their character and content. When it is said that the object of intellectual property is used at its discretion, it is understood that the owner of the right, by his own husband, by his will, without any coercion, without repression. The author may assume the obligation under the contract on the creation and use of the results of intellectual activity to create my future result of a work, invention or other intellectual activity and to give exclusive rights to the customer who does not have his own employer to use this result.

In intellectual property law, the methods of alternative resolution of their disputes are different. They are developing, including more and more new mechanisms in the category of tools, through which any dispute related to failure to fulfill its obligations or unfair performance can be resolved without going to court. In foreign countries, more than thirty methods are used in this regard. As the main alternative methods, we can cite mediation, arbitration and negotiations. One of these cases of the emergence of mediation can be noted, firstly, the abundance of excessive workload of state courts, and secondly, the possibility of quickly resolving a dispute with the help of an intermediary, while maintaining confidentiality.

Another innovation was made in the law, according to which the parties to the dispute were able to confirm an out-of-court mediation agreement with a notary. In this case, he will have the power of the execution sheet, and you can contact the bailiff directly with him. Notarization of mediation contracts is a voluntary procedure. It is carried out only with the consent of the two parties. And in the previous procedure, if the transaction was concluded in the course of proceedings and was approved by the court, then it had to be enforced. Currently, a mediation agreement approved by a notary will become an executive document and it will be possible to appeal to retired judges for reconciliation in court.

If the parties confirm the mediation agreement with a notary, then it will be possible not to bring a lawsuit to the court in case of non-execution. Such a mediation agreement automatically becomes an executive document that can be submitted to bailiffs. The acquisition of the power of the executive document with the notarization of the mediation agreement contributes to the development of the mediation Institute, which allows citizens and entrepreneurs to resolve disputes

faster, in a cross-cultural order. At the same time the notarial approval of the mediation agreement increased public interest in the mediation procedure itself.

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